

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Rivera Vargas**FIRST NAME:** Mariana**PROGRAM CODE:** MBASD**COURSE CODE :** ACA- 401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. GULMA**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (Office 365)

ACADEMIC WRITING FOR A FINANCIAL MINDSET

1) INTRODUCTION

During most of my professional experience, holding financial positions, I have consistently used an impersonal approach and passive voice. We, financials, mostly describe, follow up and analyze the development of an external entity where the witness's role in these activities lacks ownership. After studying the material provided for the course ACA - 401 I spotted two important challenges in the development of my academic writing skills. At first, personalization of the paper, "Write in a formal academic style, and sometimes, provide personal examples" (EUCLID 2015, 39). Providing personal examples implies the use of the first person singular which I have seldom done in my professional life. Secondly, using an active over a passive voice, "Use the active voice unless you specifically need to use the passive" (EUCLID 2015, 46). This requires a structural change not just in the way how I express ideas but also in the way how I process information.

Another point of interest I will address in this paper is the sources of information and its proper citation in academic writing and the accounting disclosure principle. All financial information is strictly generated under national or international standards or specific rules of economic areas and should comply with the universal accounting principles. The followed standards, rules and all relevant information regarding the source of evidence are included in a mandatory disclosure letter. Similarly, in academic compositions, the source of information has to be properly recognized in order to avoid plagiarism (EUCLID 2015, 10). In this paper, I will present the similarities between the disclosure section previously mentioned and the sources citation and bibliography in academic writing.

2) RESPONSE PAPER EMPOWERMENT: PERSONAL TOUCH AND ACTIVE VOICE

Some of the tasks I have executed in my professional life are reporting, translate facts into Key Performance Indicators (KPI's) and finally propose plans to improve these KPI's according to the entity's vision and mission. The entity is the subject of analysis and it executes and owns the obtained results, therefore, the goal is to focus the composition on the results and avoid the author's input from the background, the use of an impersonal writing style is strongly advised in this field. Opposite to this strong advice, EUCLID suggests its students to forget about that piece of advice (EUCLID 2015, 44). By combining formal academic style and the use of first person singular I can include my background in the research context, where findings would relate to my own perspective. The result of this composition will be inclusive and will transmit my own opinion when approaching the targeted public.

Another key improvement EUCLID and I seek is: "adequately interact with the provided material and show progress by composing a critical reflection." (2019, 3). My starting idea of how to write a response paper was to communicate the acquired knowledge by making a summary of what I understood. By studying course pack, I got confronted with the limitations I was experiencing and how to eliminate them, for instance, "Creative thinking encourages you to broaden your ideas. Try techniques like brainstorming or mind mapping" (EUCLID 2015, 3). Mind mapping helped me developing the topics I focused on in this paper. For me opening my mind to new techniques meant the use of active voice for expressing ideas. To balance this paper I exercise critical thinking, "encourages you to narrow the focus or scope or your ideas" (EUCLID 2015, 3), being critical helped me choose the topics that will mean major adjustments for me, rather than what (according to me) would be a topic to summarize.

3) THE SOURCES OF INFORMATION, CITATION, AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

When I read Financial Statements, audit's results or any kind of financial recommendation, the first thing I look for is the disclosure letter, because in this letter I can read under which general conditions and principles the information was collected and presented to the interested public (being the equivalent to a publication in the academic world). Based on Turabians classification of sources, I think that Financial statements can be considered as a primary source of information and audit recommendations or findings as secondary sources.

In fields such as economics, psychology, chemistry and so on, evidence consists of the data that researches collect. The primary source for those collected data are the publications that first publish them. Secondary sources are books and articles that analyze primary sources, usually written by and for other researchers (Turabian 2013, 24).

In both, academic writings and financial statements the relevance of the source is a key research criterium. To comply with this criterium for this paper I studied the latest edition of the course-pack (2015). If we apply this criterium to financial statements, we would use the data from the latest closed financial year or cycle.

In both academic and financial writing, it is mandatory to avoid plagiarism, which is. “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2015, 9). In the context of academic writing, these ideas can be statements, evidence, interviews, graphics and tables published by other authors or institutions. In the financial context, it can be information, conclusions or graphics made by another third party hired for a similar evaluation. Plagiarism can be deliberate or inadvertent, in the first case the author purposely uses somebody else’s work for his own benefit without giving the proper credit to the owner of the research. Inadvertent plagiarism denotes lack of expertise, interest (Turabian 2013, 51). Both types of plagiarism diminish the credibility of the paper, report or statement, both are ethically incorrect and are disrespectful to other researches and society in general since it deprives us of knowledge and therefore the opportunity to develop it. In the financial world, an incomplete or incorrect disclosure letter can lead to insufficient fraud detection, affecting the entity, personnel, government and hence society in general.

Giving credit to the authors of the ideas used in the academic paper is called citation, Proper citation is an effective way of preventing plagiarism and can be applied following two types: “The Bibliography style and the Parenthetical, also called In-Text style” (Turabian 2013, 87). The last step of citation is to list all the used material in the reference paragraph using the different formats accordingly, the reference paragraph is in financial compositions included in the disclosure letter.

4) CONCLUSION

This first course has introduced me to the world of academic writing, which is very different from the writing I use in my professional life as well as the type of writing I learned during the propaedeutic courses of the Master studies I followed. Although I have a lot to learn, the approach and materials EUCLID provides, set me in the right direction for a proactive development. The use of first person singular and use of the active voice have already changed the role I play in the assimilation and generation of knowledge. I look forward to keeping exercising creative thinking by expanding boundaries in the concepts I am confronted with, as well as discovering new techniques and ideas to improve my writing skills, as well as critical thinking, which will help me remain focused and within the scope of the research. Another goal is to organically comply with the writing style recommended by EUCLID, The Chicago Manual of Style.

The association between the disclosure principle and letter in financial writing and proper citation and reference section in academic writing has provided me a clear idea of the purpose, consequence, and importance of these mandatory sections in both worlds, where the quality of financial and academic writing is directly related to the respect shown to the information and its author. The lack of or incorrect handling of this

section has important ethical, legal and economic consequences writing recommendations e citation style. The constant use of citation and referencing has improved the quality of my writing, although I am far for doing it perfectly, I can to notice improvement and I am confident this improvement will remain.

REFERENCES

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